

Inclusion of a guest molecule in a tetranuclear adduct of sodium perchlorate and copper(II) complex of di-Schiff base ligand

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Abstract : The synthesis of a new sodium perchlorate adduct (1 : 3) with a copper(II) "ligand-complex" is reported in which 2-hydroxyacetophenone acts as a guest. The adduct is tetranuclear of formula $\{[(CuL)_3Na]ClO_4\}_2 \cdot C_8O_2H_8 \cdot 0.5CH_3CN$ (1). The ligand is the tetradentate di-Schiff base of 1,3-propanediamines and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (H_2L). The complex has been characterized by X-ray single crystal structure analysis. In the structure, the sodium cation has a six-coordinate distorted octahedral environment being bonded to six oxygen atoms from three Schiff base complexes. The complex exhibits reversible reductive (Cu^{II}/Cu^I ; E_{pc} , -0.914 V) and oxidative (Cu^{II}/Cu^{III} ; E_{pa} , +1.060 V respectively) responses in cyclic voltammetry. The generated Cu^I species for the complex is unstable and undergoes disproportionation to Cu^0 and Cu^{2+} .

Keywords : Copper(II), di-Schiff base ligand, $[Na^+Cu^{II}_3]$ adduct, crystal structure, spectral properties, electrochemistry.

Introduction

The field of inclusion chemistry¹ that includes the design, synthesis, and structure determination of a large number of host-guest compounds has seen rapid growth in the past 10 years². The formation and stability of inclusion compounds depend on the strengths and directions of intermolecular forces found in the host-guest assembly, and crystal structure determination gives information about topology and packing, which affect thermal stability and kinetics of formation and decomposition. These complexes are ordered molecular aggregates associated with two or more molecules, ions or coordination compounds through intermolecular interactions^{3,4}. Examples of host molecules in supramolecular chemistry include inter alia crown ethers, cryptates, calixarenes and cyclodextrines (CDs)^{3,5-7}. Crown ethers, cryptands, and related ligands are the most important class of complexing agents for alkali metal ions and consequently structure/selectivity studies usually focus on such systems⁸⁻¹⁰. Furthermore, such types of complexes can stabilize a guest molecule by supramolecular interactions¹¹.

Recently we synthesized a tetranuclear adduct of

$NaClO_4$ with $[CuL]$, where $H_2L = N,N'$ -bis(α -methylsalicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine¹². A different synthetic procedure reveals that this tetranuclear species can incorporate a guest molecule (*o*-hydroxyacetophenone). Here, we report the formation and crystal structure of this adduct, $\{[(CuL)_3Na]ClO_4\}_2 \cdot C_8O_2H_8 \cdot 0.5CH_3CN$ (see Scheme 1). To our knowledge, no such heterometallic adduct of a "ligand complex" precursor together with a guest molecule has been previously reported.

Experimental

Starting materials :

o-Hydroxyacetophenone and 1,3-propanediamine were purchased from Lancaster and were of reagent grade. They were used without further purification.

Caution! Perchlorate salts of metal complexes with organic ligands are potentially explosive. Only a small amount of material should be prepared and it should be handled with care.

Synthesis of the Schiff base ligand H_2L :

The di-Schiff base ligand, H_2L was prepared by stan-

Scheme. 1. Synthesis route to complex 1.

standard methods. Briefly, 5 mmol of 1,3-propanediamine (0.41 mL) was mixed with 10 mmol of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (1.21 mL) in ethanol (20 mL). The resulting solution was refluxed for *ca.* 2 h, and allowed to cool. The yellow ethanolic solution was used directly for complex formation.

Synthesis of the complex [CuL] :

To an ethanolic solution (10 mL) of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.852 g, 5 mmol), was added an ethanolic solution of H₂L (5 mmol, 20 mL) to prepare the complex CuL as reported earlier¹³.

Synthesis of the complex $\{[(\text{CuL})_3\text{Na}]\text{ClO}_4\}_2 \cdot \text{C}_8\text{O}_2\text{H}_8 \cdot 0.5\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ (1) :

The "ligand complex" CuL (1.116 g, 3 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol (15 mL) and then 5 mL of water solution of sodium perchlorate (0.140 g, 1 mmol) and another 5 mL ethanolic solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.12 mL, 2 mmol) were added to the solution, stirred for 30 min and allowed to stand for 1 h. A gray colored compound was then found separated at the bottom of the beaker. The compound was dissolved in acetonitrile solution and left overnight when X-ray quality single crystals appeared. The crystals were isolated, washed with Et₂O and dried in vacuum desiccator containing anhydrous CaCl₂. (Yield : 0.622 g, 47%) *Anal.* Calcd. for. C₁₂₃H_{129.5}Cl₂Cu₆N_{12.5}Na₂O₂₂ (2633.01) : Calculated : C, 56.06; H, 4.92; N, 6.64; Found : C, 55.81; H, 4.87, N 6.77, UV/Vis (MeCN) : λ_{max} = 272, 348 and 532 nm; IR : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1594 cm⁻¹, $\nu(\text{ClO}_4^-)$ 1089 cm⁻¹.

Crystal data collection and refinement :

31394 independent data were collected with MoK α radiation at 150 K using the Oxford Diffraction X-Calibur CCD System. The crystal was positioned at 50 mm from

the CCD. 321 frames were measured with a counting time of 10 s. Data analysis was carried out with the CrysAlis program¹⁴. The structure was solved using direct methods with the Shelxs97 program¹⁵. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. Absorption corrections were carried out using the ABSPACK program¹⁶. The structure was refined on F² using Shelxl97¹⁵ to R1 0.0672; wR2 0.1664 for 9175 reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$. Details of crystallographic data and refinement of the complex was summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and refinement details of the complex 1

Formula	C ₁₂₃ H _{129.5} Cl ₂ Cu ₆ N _{12.5} Na ₂ O ₂₂
Formula weight	2633.01
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	12.0771(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	20.4159(10)
<i>c</i> (Å)	25.2903(9)
α (°)	103.609(4)
β (°)	91.531(3)
γ (°)	96.606(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	6011.0(4)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D_c</i> (g cm ⁻³)	1.455
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.169
<i>R</i> (int)	0.0672
No. of unique data	10183
No. of data with $I > 2\sigma(I)$	9715
R1, wR2 for $I > 2\sigma(I)$	0.0558, 0.1698
GOF on F ²	0.844

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 series II CHN analyzer. IR spectra in KBr pellets (4000–500 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. The electronic absorption spectra (1200–350 nm) in acetonitrile solution were recorded in a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical studies were carried out using a Sycopel model AEW2 1820F/S instrument. The measurements were performed at 300 K in acetonitrile solution containing 0.2 M TEAP and 10^{-3} M complex deoxygenated by bubbling with nitrogen. The working, counter, and reference electrodes used were a platinum wire, a platinum coil, and an SCE respectively.

Results and discussion

Synthesis, IR and UV-Vis spectra of the complex :

The di-Schiff-base ligand (H_2L) and its Cu^{II} complex (CuL) were synthesized using the reported methods¹³. This “ligand complex” on reaction with sodium perchlorate in the presence of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in EtOH- H_2O medium (4 : 1, v/v) resulted in the tetranuclear inclusion complex **1** $\{[(\text{CuL})_3\text{Na}]\text{ClO}_4\}_2 \cdot \text{C}_8\text{O}_2\text{H}_8 \cdot 0.5 \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ by self-assembly (see Scheme 1). Besides elemental analysis, the complex was initially characterized by IR spectra. The appearance of the characteristic intense peaks for perchlorate in the IR spectra at 1088 cm^{-1} clearly indicates the formation of the complex. The rest of the spectral pattern and band position of the complex was very similar to that of the ligand complex. A strong and sharp band of the complex due to the azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group of the Schiff base appears at 1594 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectra of the complex, measured in acetonitrile solution, displays a single absorption band at 532 nm. The positions of these bands are consistent with the observed square-based geometry around the copper centers. The intense band at about 348 and 272 nm for complex **1** indicates ligand to metal charge-transfer and intra ligand charge transfer, respectively.

Electrochemical studies :

The cyclic voltammogram of the complex **1** in acetonitrile solution displays an irreversible reductive response (E_{pc} at -0.914 V) during cathodic scan for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple. During the anodic potential scan, an oxidative

response at *ca.* -0.299 V with a very narrow width and high peak current is observed. At more positive potential a quasi-reversible oxidative response at 1.060 V (E_{pc}), 0.819 V (E_{pa}) and 0.935 V ($E_{1/2}$) (versus SCE) (Fig. 1). The response at -0.299 V is typical of the anodic stripping of copper. Therefore, it may be inferred that complex **1** undergoes reduction to Cu^{I} complex which subsequently undergoes disproportionation to Cu^0 and Cu^{2+} . The lower values of E_{pc} and the instability of the Cu^{I} complexes are in agreement with the very small tetrahedral distortion in Cu^{II} units as Cu^{I} is stabilized in tetrahedral environment¹⁷⁻²⁰.

Fig. 1. The cyclic voltammogram of complex **1** in acetonitrile solution.

Description of the structure :

The structure contains two discrete independent $[(\text{CuL})_3]\text{Na}^+$ cations, two perchlorate anions with 50% occupancy, one *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and one acetonitrile molecule with 30% occupancy. The structures of the two cations A and B are equivalent with dimensions in the metal coordination spheres compared in Table 2 while the structure of cation A is shown in Fig. 2.

The structure of the $[(\text{CuL})_3\text{Na}]^+$ cation involves three CuL moieties surrounding a sodium cation. The sodium cation is six-coordinate being bonded to three pairs of oxygen atoms from the ligands. Thus the sodium ion bridges to three copper atoms each through two oxygen atoms. The environment of the six-coordinate sodium ion is regular in geometry if not in bond lengths. Thus there

Table 2. Dimensions, distances (Å), angles (deg) in the metal coordination spheres of complex 1

	A	B
Cu(1)–O(11)	1.920(3)	1.910(3)
Cu(1)–O(33)	1.927(3)	1.922(3)
Cu(1)–N(20)	1.996(4)	1.986(4)
Cu(1)–N(24)	1.989(4)	1.964(4)
Cu(1)–O(41)	2.475(4)	2.575(4)
Cu(2)–O(41)	1.910(3)	1.914(3)
Cu(2)–O(63)	1.889(4)	1.916(4)
Cu(2)–N(50)	1.979(4)	1.971(5)
Cu(2)–N(54)	1.967(5)	1.970(4)
Cu(2)–O(11)	2.689(4)	2.576(4)
Cu(3)–O(71)	1.923(3)	1.911(4)
Cu(3)–O(93)	1.896(4)	1.893(4)
Cu(3)–N(80)	1.970(5)	1.979(5)
Cu(3)–N(84)	1.967(5)	1.991(4)
Na(4)–O(63)	2.262(5)	2.263(4)
Na(4)–O(93)	2.278(4)	2.277(4)
Na(4)–O(11)	2.455(4)	2.452(4)
Na(4)–O(41)	2.775(4)	2.800(4)
Na(4)–O(33)	2.300(4)	2.258(4)
Na(4)–O(71)	2.409(4)	2.388(4)
O(11)–Cu(1)–O(33)	87.74(14)	88.42(15)
O(11)–Cu(1)–N(24)	171.26(17)	171.71(17)
O(33)–Cu(1)–N(24)	91.10(16)	90.23(17)
O(11)–Cu(1)–N(20)	89.10(16)	89.16(17)
O(33)–Cu(1)–N(20)	155.26(18)	158.38(19)
N(24)–Cu(1)–N(20)	95.51(18)	95.07(19)
O(63)–Cu(2)–O(41)	89.33(16)	89.54(16)
O(63)–Cu(2)–N(54)	92.1(2)	92.03(18)
O(41)–Cu(2)–N(54)	161.99(18)	165.76(19)
O(63)–Cu(2)–N(50)	153.54(19)	153.71(19)
O(41)–Cu(2)–N(50)	88.20(17)	88.37(17)
N(54)–Cu(2)–N(50)	98.3(2)	96.35(19)
O(93)–Cu(3)–O(71)	85.54(15)	86.18(15)
O(93)–Cu(3)–N(80)	166.8(2)	171.1(2)
O(71)–Cu(3)–N(80)	88.84(17)	89.46(18)
O(93)–Cu(3)–N(84)	89.86(18)	88.83(18)
O(71)–Cu(3)–N(84)	170.08(17)	170.45(17)
N(80)–Cu(3)–N(84)	97.4(2)	96.5(2)
O(63)–Na(4)–O(93)	99.54(16)	101.62(15)
O(63)–Na(4)–O(33)	137.96(16)	138.95(16)
O(93)–Na(4)–O(33)	106.39(15)	104.74(14)
O(63)–Na(4)–O(71)	105.75(15)	105.34(15)
O(93)–Na(4)–O(71)	67.13(13)	67.64(13)
O(33)–Na(4)–O(71)	114.58(15)	113.55(16)

Table-2 (contd.)

O(63)–Na(4)–O(11)	86.24(14)	82.73(13)
O(93)–Na(4)–O(11)	174.09(16)	173.40(15)
O(33)–Na(4)–O(11)	68.13(13)	68.98(13)
O(71)–Na(4)–O(11)	112.61(14)	116.24(15)
O(63)–Na(4)–O(41)	63.08(13)	63.36(13)
O(93)–Na(4)–O(41)	118.92(15)	115.84(15)
O(33)–Na(4)–O(41)	75.44(12)	76.92(13)
O(71)–Na(4)–O(41)	167.32(14)	168.37(14)
O(11)–Na(4)–O(41)	62.64(12)	61.52(13)

Fig. 2. The structure of cation A, [(CuL)₃Na]⁺ in complex 1 with ellipsoids at 30% probability. The structure of cation B is equivalent.

are three short bond lengths to O(63), O(93) and O(33) with distances in the range 2.258(4)–2.300(4) Å in the two molecules, then longer bonds to O(71) at 2.409(4), 2.388(4) Å and O(11) of 2.455(4), 2.452(4) Å and then a much longer bond to O(41) of 2.775(4), 2.800(4) Å for unit A, B respectively. In the sodium coordination sphere, there are two *trans* angles close to 180° but the third potentially *trans* angle O(63)–Na(4)–O(33) differs considerably at 137.9(2), 138.9(2)° in the two molecules. The three Na...Cu distances are slightly irregular with Na(4)···Cu(1) 3.161(2), 3.162(2) Å, Na(4)···Cu(2) 3.205(2), 3.180(2) Å and Na(4)···Cu(3) 3.262(2), 3.269(2) Å. The environments of Cu(1) and Cu(2) are similar to each other but different from that of Cu(3). Both copper atoms are bonded to a ligand L and form four strong bonds in an equatorial plane with Cu–O and Cu–N in the range 1.910(3)–1.927(3) Å and 1.964(4)–1.996(4) Å res-

pectively. The two CuL units are then connected via the weak coordination of the oxygen atom of a phenoxido group bonded to the other unit in an axial position at distances in the range 2.475(4)–2.689(4) Å, thus completing the square pyramidal environment. The phenoxido oxygen atoms O(41) and O(11) are therefore coordinated to three metal ions (one sodium and two copper), an arrangement which is very rare^{12,21}. The geometry of Cu(1) and Cu(2) is confirmed as square pyramidal via calculation of the Addison parameters²² 0.267, 0.222 for Cu(1) and 0.141, 0.201 for Cu(2) in unit A and B respectively.

By contrast, the geometry around Cu(3) is four-coordinate square planar with a tetrahedral distortion in which the r.m.s deviation of donor atoms from their plane is 0.166 and 0.128 Å respectively for unit A and B. The metal atoms Cu(3A) and Cu(3B) are 0.027(1) and 0.004(1) Å from the square plane respectively. This geometry is also confirmed by the so-called τ_4 index that measures the distortion between a perfect tetrahedron ($\tau_4 = 1$) and a perfect square planar geometry ($\tau_4 = 0$) with the formula: $\tau_4 = [360^\circ - (A + B)]/141^\circ$, being A and B (in °) the two largest angles around the central metal in the complex²³. The τ_4 value for Cu(3A) and Cu(3B) is 0.164 and 0.138 respectively, confirming a slightly distorted square planar geometry for this metal center. In the com-

plex, the Cu(1)···Cu(2) distances are 3.546(2), 3.562(2) Å, significantly shorter than Cu(1)···Cu(3) at 6.352(2), 6.316(2) Å and Cu(2)···Cu(3) at 5.847(1), 5.928(1) Å. The dimensions of the cations, when compared to those of the cation in the previously reported complex¹² without the guest molecule show no significant differences.

The structure also contains one solvent molecule of acetonitrile and one of guest *o*-hydroxyacetophenone. The guest molecule is stabilized by inter-molecular (C–H···O) hydrogen bonding between H(86D) of C(86B) with O(9) with the distance of 2.519(10) Å (Fig. 3a) and a very weak C–H··· π interaction involving H(56B) of C(56A) with the phenyl ring of the guest molecule at a distance of 3.23 Å. The nitrogen atom N(21) of the acetonitrile solvent molecule forms a hydrogen bond with a methyl proton, H(19F) of the B unit at 3.455(18) Å (Fig. 3b). The C_{sp^2} -H/ π interactions are also found in the complex as given in Table 3. Each tetranuclear unit shows three C_{sp^2} -H/ π interactions similar to those reported earlier¹². The two tetranuclear units are joined together with C–H···O hydrogen bonding interactions (Fig. 3a) involving O(71) in both units which interacts with H(79D) and H(79C) respectively for unit A and B at distances of 2.72 and 2.60 Å.

Table 3. C_{sp^2} -H/ π distances (Å) and angles (°) of the complex 1

Cation	X–H···Cg	H···Cg	Gamma	$\angle X-H\cdots Cg$	X···Cg
A	C(53A)–H(53B)···Cg(11)	2.94	15.94	145	3.773(8)
B	C(53B)–H(53C)···Cg(27)	2.91	13.44	141	3.718(7)
A	C(56A)–H(56A)···Cg(16)	2.84	10.41	155	3.732(7)
B	C(56B)–H(56F)···Cg(32)	2.91	8.35	150	3.773(7)
A	C(79A)–H(79B)···Cg(30)	2.82	10.90	141	3.617(6)
B	C(81B)–H(81C)···Cg(15)	2.98	16.09	143	3.801(7)

Fig. 3. (a) Supramolecular interactions involving guest molecule and two tetranuclear units; (b) Inter-molecular H-bonding interaction between the complex and acetonitrile.

Conclusions :

In summary, the preparation of one discrete cluster containing two $[\text{Na}^{\text{I}}\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}_3]$ structural units with a guest molecule of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone has been reported. The compound has been formed via self-assembly of square planar "ligand complex" of the type $[\text{CuL}]$ with the Na^{I} acceptor. The guest molecule is stabilized in the complex by inter-molecular (C-H...O) H-bonding and C-H... π interactions. The formation of an alkali metal ion adduct of such a "ligand complex" with a guest molecule is quite unique.

Appendix A

Supplementary material :

CCDC 838044 contains the supplementary crystallographic data of the complex. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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